

Numerical Methods in Fins with Excel and MATLAB

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, numerical methods are applied through the implementation of finite difference routines using Excel and MATLAB to calculate the heating and cooling times of a square plate supporting fins using aluminum and steel as materials.

Four cases are analyzed for the same fin model: the first one is heating with hot air, the second one is heating with hot air, the third case is heating with air and then with air but reducing the fin thickness by half, and the fourth case is cold air cooling, but in all cases the plate area remains unchanged.

Numerical methods are used as the mathematical tool to solve the system of equations derived from applying an energy balance to the nodes in the fin. These solutions provide temperature as a function of time for each material, based on the fin design. MATLAB was used to develop the simulation code, and Excel was employed to implement the equations in each cell.

The results obtained in this study align with findings from existing literature. This approach serves as a valuable tool for mechanical engineering students interested in simulating thermodynamic effects in materials and extending the analysis to estimate heating or cooling times, as well as the efficiency of fins made from other materials.

KEYWORDS: Conduction, Convection, Excel, Fin, MATLAB, Methods Numerical, Node, Temperature

1. INTRODUCTION

Fins are extended surfaces that improve heat transfer efficiency [1]. In this study, a fin was theoretically designed using two materials, aluminum and steel, in order to compare the time required to reach a certain temperature.

The problem addressed is the solution of the system of equations established at the nodes of the fin. For the numerical solution, numerical methods [2] are applied by implementing routines in Excel and MATLAB [3], and the variables under study are plotted. In addition, the process is outlined in detail, which will be useful for students who wish to replicate the theoretical calculations using other materials with similar designs, since some texts address the subject but do not illustrate the steps to follow. Previous studies have focused on techniques, simulation methods, and the effectiveness of fins, making this field an interesting topic of research in engineering [4].

Finally, the results obtained are compared with the theoretical references, and the conclusions of this study are presented.

2. THEORY

2.1 Heat transfer

A fin is an extended surface that increases heat transfer, with the purpose of efficiently heating or cooling materials. The types of fins include transverse fins, which are used for heating or cooling, and longitudinal fins, which are used in tubes with viscous fluids, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Diagram of the flap on the plate, own elaboration.

Heat is thermal energy that is transferred from a hotter system to a cooler system in contact, while temperature is a measure of the average kinetic energy of the atoms or molecules in the system; these two concepts are key in this study.

The forms of heat transfer are conduction, convection, and radiation.

Conduction is the transfer of heat through direct contact between particles of one material and those of another [5]; there is no transfer of matter between the bodies. The amount of heat transferred by conduction is calculated using Fourier’s law.

$$\dot{Q} = kA \frac{\Delta T}{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

Where \dot{Q} is the heat transferred per time interval, k is the thermal conductivity constant that depends on the material, A is the area, and ε is the thickness of the film.

The thermal conductivity constant for aluminum is $238.6 \frac{W}{m \cdot ^\circ K}$ and for steel $47.7 \frac{W}{m \cdot ^\circ K}$.

Convection: It is the transport of heat by means of the movement of a fluid, whether gaseous or liquid [6]. The transfer occurs in terms of Newton's law of cooling, which states that a body loses its heat at a rate proportional to the temperature difference between the body and its surroundings [7].

$$\dot{Q} = hA \Delta T \quad (2)$$

Where \dot{Q} is the rate of heat transfer by convection, A is the surface area and h is the convection coefficient for hot air is $200 \frac{W}{m^2 \cdot ^\circ K}$ and for water is $1000 \frac{W}{m^2 \cdot ^\circ K}$ and is not a fluid property [1].

Finally, the other form of heat transfer is radiation, which is the emission, propagation and transfer of energy in the form of electromagnetic waves in any medium. In this study this form of heat transfer is not considered.

2.2 Numerical methods

To illustrate mathematically the problem to be solved, we will take a real physical situation, which is to obtain the temperature T at a specific point (node) in a system surrounded by 4 different temperatures, as illustrated in Fig 2.

Figure 2. Scheme of the system to find the temperature T in the center surrounded by different temperatures (not to scale).

To find the temperature T at the center, the average of the temperatures surrounding it is obtained; in other words, T depends on the environment, and the equation to solve is

$$4T = 60^\circ C + 10^\circ C + 40^\circ C + 20^\circ C \quad (3)$$

thus, finding that this temperature $T_1 = 32.5 \text{ } ^\circ C$.

Now suppose we want to find the temperatures T_1 and T_2 in the system illustrated in figure 3 with the temperatures shown.

Figure 3. Scheme of the system to find the temperatures T_1 and T_2 surrounded by different temperatures (not to scale).

For this case, the system of equations to be posed is

$$4T_1 = 60^\circ C + 20^\circ C + 10^\circ C + T_2 \quad (4)$$

$$4T_2 = 60^\circ C + 40^\circ C + 20^\circ C + T_1 \quad (5)$$

When solving this system of equations by one of the known methods, we obtain that $T_1 = 32 \text{ } ^\circ C$ and $T_2 = 38 \text{ } ^\circ C$.

If it is desired to determine the four temperatures in the system shown in figure 4, the system of equations to solutions is

Figure 4. Scheme of the system to find the temperatures T_1, T_2, T_3 , and T_4 surrounded by different temperatures (not to scale).

$$4T_1 = 70^\circ C + T_2 + T_3 \quad (6)$$

$$4T_2 = 100^\circ C + T_1 + T_4 \quad (7)$$

$$4T_3 = 30^\circ C + T_1 + T_4 \quad (8)$$

$$4T_4 = 60^\circ C + T_2 + T_3 \quad (9)$$

The solution of this system can be done by any of the known methods for systems of linear equations, such as substitution, equalization, elimination, or Cramer, among others. For these equations, the solution is obtained as follows: $T_1 = 33.75^\circ C$, $T_2 = 41.25^\circ C$, $T_3 = 23.75^\circ C$ y $T_4 = 31.25^\circ C$.

In systems with a larger number of equations and more variables, the solution requires the application of numerical methods, among which Gauss-Seidel is the equivalent in the solution of systems of linear equations to the method of successive approximations in the solution of algebraic and transcendental equations or the use of computer programs that implement iteration routines based on recurrence relations.

2.3 Temperature equations at each node

Next, the equations for the different types of nodes are established according to the meshing in the fin. To obtain the stability criterion in the iteration of the program, it is necessary to find the parameter τ through the equation [1]:

$$\tau = \frac{\alpha_t \Delta t}{\Delta x^2} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\alpha_t = \frac{k}{\rho C_p} \tag{11}$$

The values of the constants are shown in Table 1 for steel and aluminum

Table 1. Constants for steel and aluminum

Material	Densit y $\rho \left[\frac{Kg}{m^3} \right]$	Conductivi ty $K \left[\frac{W}{m \cdot K} \right]$	Specif ic Heat $C_p \left[\frac{J}{Kg \cdot ^\circ K} \right]$	Thermal diffusivity $\alpha_t \left[\frac{m^2}{s} \right]$
Aluminu m	2692	238.6	922.7	0.000097
Steel	7838	47.7	450.6	0.000023

The equation for the energy balance at each node is

$$\dot{Q}_{cond} + \dot{Q}_{conv} + E_{gen,elem} - \frac{\Delta_{elem}}{\Delta t} = 0 \tag{12}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 shows the nodes in the fin design, while Figure 6 presents the color coding used to identify the types of nodes selected.

Figure 5. Nodes on the fin model.

NODE 1	
NODE 2	
NODE 3	
NODE 4	
NODE 5	
NODE 6	
NODE 7	

Figure 6. Color code to identify the type of node.

The measures in a node are:

$$\Delta x = \Delta y = 5 \text{ mm} \text{ and } \Delta z = 2 \text{ mm}.$$

The finite difference formulation of heat conduction in a plate is performed by establishing the energy balance and solving the resulting equations by iteration. The method consists of dividing volume elements and applying the energy balance to each of them, this is done by selecting the nodes in which the temperature is to be determined.

In particular, for the cases analyzed, the fin is attached to a square plate with a side length of 0.15 m. Two materials,

aluminum and steel, are considered. For the heating process, the fin starts at 15 °C and is heated with hot air until it reaches 100 °C. For the cooling process, the same fin and materials start at 100 °C and are cooled with air at 5 °C. For both heating and cooling, the convection coefficient is 200 W/(m²·K).

The energy balance equations (12) for each type of fin node are [8]:

Node 1.

$$T_1^{i+1} = T_1^i \left(1 - \frac{2\tau h \Delta x}{k} - 2\tau - \frac{\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} \right) + \tau(T_S + T_E) + \frac{\tau h \Delta x}{k}(T_W + T_N) + \frac{\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} T_\infty \tag{13}$$

Node 2.

$$T_2^{i+1} = T_2^i \left(1 - \frac{\tau h \Delta x}{k} - 3\tau - \frac{\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} \right) + \tau T_S + \frac{\tau h \Delta x}{k} T_N + \tau(T_E + T_W) + \frac{\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} T_\infty \tag{14}$$

Node 3.

$$T_3^{i+1} = T_3^i \left(1 - \frac{\tau h \Delta x}{k} - 3\tau - \frac{\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} \right) + \tau(T_N + T_S + T_E) + \frac{\tau h \Delta x}{k} T_W + \frac{\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} T_\infty \tag{15}$$

Node 4.

$$T_4^{i+1} = T_4^i \left(1 - 4\tau - \frac{\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} \right) + \tau(T_N + T_E + T_S + T_W) + \frac{\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} T_\infty \tag{16}$$

Node 5.

$$T_5^{i+1} = T_5^i \left(1 - \frac{\tau h \Delta x}{3k} - \frac{2}{3}\tau - \frac{2\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} \right) + \frac{\tau h \Delta x}{3k}(T_N + T_W) + \frac{\tau}{3}(T_N + T_W) + \frac{\tau}{3}(T_S + T_E) + \frac{2\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} T_\infty \tag{17}$$

Node 6.

$$T_6^{i+1} = T_6^i \left(1 - \frac{\tau h \Delta x}{k} - 2\tau - \frac{2\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} \right) + \tau(T_N + T_E) + \frac{\tau h \Delta x}{k} T_W + \frac{2\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} T_\infty \tag{18}$$

Node 7.

$$T_7^{i+1} = T_7^i \left(1 - 3\tau - \frac{2\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} \right) + \tau(T_N + T_E + T_W) + \frac{2\tau h \Delta x^2}{k \Delta z} T_\infty \tag{19}$$

Table 2 shows the values of the parameter τ , the critical values are located at node 4 highlighted with color in the table.

Table 2. Parameter τ for aluminum and steel

Node	Parameter τ	
	Aluminum	Steel
Node 1	0.49532904	0.48973301
Node 2	0.33171139	0.32537517
Node 3	0.33171139	0.32537517
Node 4	0.24934685	0.24676668
Node 5	1.45133820	1.28456014
Node 6	0.49379139	0.47041420
Node 7	0.33102109	0.32207968

Figure 7 shows a snapshot of the results obtained in Excel of the temperatures at the different nodes when implementing

Figure 12. Temperature versus time graph for aluminum fin heated with hot water.

Figure 13. Temperature versus time graph for steel fin heated with hot water.

Third case: heating of the fin with air at 100 °C, the fin is at an initial temperature of 15 °C, but the fin thickness has been reduced by half, i.e. 0.001 m in both materials. The result is shown in Figure 14 and Figure 15.

Figure 14. Temperature versus time graph for aluminum fin heated with hot air half the thickness.

Figure 15. Temperature versus time graph for steel fin heated with hot air half the thickness.

Fourth case: cooling of the fin with air at 15 °C; the fin is at an initial temperature of 100 °C. The result is shown in Figure 16 and Figure 17.

Figure 16. Temperature versus time graph for the aluminum fin cooled with cold air.

Figure 17. Temperature versus time graph for the cold air-cooled steel fin.

Table 3 shows a summary of the times to reach the temperature of the surrounding fluid in heating the coldest node of the fin or in cooling, the time to reach the stable equilibrium temperature of the hottest node.

The graphs were obtained in MATLAB.

Table 3. Times for aluminum and steel

Material	Aluminum	Steel
Air heating	15.3 s	42.5 s
Water heating	6.0 s	13.0 s
Heating with air half of the thickness	12.5 s	29.3 s
Air cooling	3.2 s	17.9 s

The graphs in Figures 18, 19, 20 and 21 were made in Excel for aluminum and steel fin heating. As can be seen, the values to reach the temperatures are similar to those obtained in MATLAB.

Figure 18. Temperature vs. time graph of aluminum fin with hot air program in Excel

Figure 19. Temperature versus time graph of steel fin with hot air program in Excel

Figure 20. Temperature versus time graph of aluminum fin with hot water program in Excel.

Figure 21. Temperature versus time graph of steel fin with hot water program in Excel

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

A fin model was designed in two materials, aluminum and steel, to measure heating and cooling. Numerical methods were used to solve the equations by implementing them in two programs, Excel and MATLAB. In both programs, it is possible to analyze the behavior of each node over time as the fin approaches a state of thermal equilibrium.

In this article, the results show that aluminum heats up faster than steel due to its high thermal conductivity. In the case of heating, the fins heat up more quickly with water than with air, as demonstrated in this study. Reducing the fin thickness decreases the heating time because it increases heat transfer by conduction. For cooling, the temperature decreases faster in aluminum than in steel.

The Gauss-Seidel method is a numerical technique that can be implemented in programming to solve systems of linear equations, such as those encountered in heat transfer analysis. The results obtained using Excel and MATLAB are similar,

and the choice of program depends on the user's familiarity with each. These simulations can also be programmed in FORTRAN or Python, or performed using software such as ANSYS Fluent or COMSOL Multiphysics.

Finally, the design of fins allows us to check the heat transfer laws, and they are useful for heating or cooling plates with different materials, and their application is in temperature reduction in engines [10].

This article is intended to serve as a helpful resource for illustrating the fin heat transfer technique.

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